

"THE EFFECT OF A RUBBERIZED MATRIX ON THE
DAMPING CAPACITY OF CFRP"

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Summary

Rubber modified resin blends incorporating 7.5% HYCAR liquid rubber are used to make high strength unidirectional CFRP laminates. Damping tests are performed on laminates incorporating both regular and rubber modified resins. Tensile testing, fiber volume determination and dynamic mechanical analysis are carried out. Mechanical properties of both types of laminates are equally high. Damping results correlate with fiber volume fractions but insignificant changes in damping capacity between regular and modified resin laminates is found at high fiber volume fractions.

Introduction

Due mainly to its high specific strength and modulus, the carbon graphite composites are finding an ever increasing number of applications in the aerospace industry and are deepening their inroads into the more widespread automotive and recreational equipment markets.

For its many strengths, CFRP composites also have their weak points in terms of low elongation to failure, low energy absorption and brittle failure in fracture. For structures subject to forced excitations it is exceedingly important that the internal damping of the composites be as high as possible thereby reducing the vibrational amplitudes and inhibiting resonant modes from inflicting damage.

The works of Gibson, Chaturvedi and Sun [1], Nelson and Hancock [2], and Gibson [3], indicates that damping stems from the interaction at the fiber / matrix interface and is largely dependent on shear strains and the viscoelastic properties of the matrix.

In an effort to take better advantage of the matrix contribution postulated we are in the process of investigating the effects of adding rubber based modifiers into the matrix prior to consolidation of the composite.

Much research on the fracture of both rubberized resins and rubberized matrix composites has been performed which can be built upon and extended to predict the damping behaviour of such composites. The works of Kunz-Douglass, Beaumont, and Ashby [4], Bascom, et al [5], have shown that fracture toughness gains more than an order of magnitude over the base resin are possible. More modest gains can be realized when the toughened resin is used in carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates [6]. Meeks [7] indicated that the corresponding decrease in strength and modulus of rubberized resin formulations is minimal when balanced against the gains in toughness obtained. Wells and Hancox [8] presented data on CFRP containing up to 35% polyurethane rubber. They found acceptable trade-offs between impact energy gains and the level of mechanical properties retained at rubber additions up to 30%. Although a downward trend in the mechanical properties is realized, CFRP laminates fabricated from such modified resins could reasonably be expected to yield similar attractive trade-offs in terms of damping by the very fact that these resins already contain some of the necessary mechanisms that support increased energy dissipation under loading. The goal of this work is to assess the feasibility of achieving significantly higher damping while retaining the important mechanical and physical properties of baseline CFRP materials.

Experimental Details

The investigations being performed involve the widely used Union Carbide T-300 fiber imbedded in a matrix of both conventional high performance resin, and rubberized modifications thereof. A machine has been built that allows the fabrication of a high quality narrow tape of unidirectional prepreg material which is subsequently laid up into a sample coupon, vacuum bagged and autoclave cured. Testing is performed for damping, tensile properties and fiber content. Dynamic mechanical analysis has also been carried out.

Resin Preparation

The resin system selected for prepregging was CIBA's high performance Araldite MY720 resin (N,N,N',N'-Tetraglycidyl-4,4' methylene-bisbenzenamine) with CIBA HT 976 (DDS) hardner (4,4' - Diaminodiphenyl sulfone) in the ratio of 52 parts by weight (pbw) hardner to 100 pbw resin. Reactive group content is 125g / equivalent. For the rubberized matrix a single grade of liquid rubber additive, B.F. Goodrich's HYCAR CTBN 1300 x 8 (carboxyl-terminated butadienne acrylonitrile) containing 18% acrylonitrile, 2.37% carboxyl, a functionality of 1.85 and .050 equivalents per hundred of rubber was added in a concentration of 7.5% to the above mixture. MY 720 is clear, brown and has a consistency like cold molasses (20000cp @ 50°C) while HT 976 is a fine tan powder with a 175°C melting point. HYCAR liquid rubber is translucent gold-brown with a consistency similar to "honey". To attain a workable mixture from these components, the resin was heated to 85°C and 40 pbw of a 50%-50% MEK / acetone solution was stirred in. This brought the viscosity down to a level where subsequent dissolution of the hardner and liquid rubber was straightforward. The shelf-life of MY 720/HT 976 is over 6 months at room temperature. During prepregging the resin bath is held at 85°C and fine adjustments are made to retain a desirable viscosity range by adding small quantities of the aforementioned diluents.

Prepregging

A small machine, constructed at Concordia University's Composite Materials Research Laboratory, was used produce prepregged T-300 / MY-720

Figure 1 - Laboratory prepreg tape fabricating machine.

Figure 2 - Prepreg machine heated bath and backing paper applicator close-up.

Arrangement "A"

Arrangement "B"

- Legend:
- 1. Vacuum bag
 - 2. Heavy bleeder material
 - 3. Light bleeder material
 - 4. Caul plate (stainless steel)
 - 5. Prepreg layup
 - 6. Release film
 - 7. Preperforated film
 - 8. Pressure sensitive sealant
 - 9. Base plate (stainless steel)
 - 10. Fine teflon release film

Figure 3 - Bagging arrangements for low and high fiber content in laminates

unidirectional tape approximately 50 mm. wide and 0.20 mm. thick. (Figure 1 & 2). Between 5 m - 10 m of tape were produced at one time allowing for the production of two or four specimens. A heated bath for the resin was used to attain the required impregnation viscosity. Such a bath is advantageous because immediately after the prepreg was layered between its waxed backing paper, the resin cooled and thickened allowing relative ease in subsequent handling steps. An alternative technique to obtain the required impregnation viscosity is to use more diluents, however this technique produces prepregs that don't hold together well because they are too runny. Excess resin was squeezed off the prepreg by laying the prepreg on a smooth table and slowly pushing a squeegee along the backing paper while warming the area immediately in front of the squeegee to about 80°C using a "heat gun type" hot air blower. Graphite tape thickness at this point was uniformly .17-.19 mm. The prepreg was left at room conditions (21°C, 30% R.H.) for 4 days while the solvents volatilized and the resin reassumed a tar-like consistency. This prepreg then exhibited good tackiness upon contact with finger warmth. Finished prepreg was stored at -5°C until ready for use. Four month old samples showed no discernable changes.

Lay-up and Cure

Specimen lay-up and consolidation was performed using a vacuum bagging/autoclave curing technique. The bagging sequence shown in figure 3 was performed according to two variations, "A" providing a low fiber content and "B" providing a high fiber content. The cure cycle is summarized in table I and figure 4. The autoclave, which also doubles as a vacuum chamber for the damping tests; is shown in figure 5.

The appearance of cured specimens was generally very smooth, flat and uniform. Voids were not apparent to the naked eye, and only a few pinholes were discernible under a 100 X stereoscope. Early specimens (#6, #7) showed spots of fiber waviness. This was due to non-uniformities along sections of the prepreg. Waviness problems were rectified for the later specimens.

Material Testing

All specimens were tensile tested in an MTS system according to ASTM D 3039 at a strain rate of .25% / min. using tapered end tabs of 3.2 mm thick SMC-R25 bonded with CIBA Araldite XP-3457 epoxy adhesive. A number of fiber volume fraction tests were initially performed according to ASTM D 3171, however, they were abandoned in favor of using much simpler density tests (ASTM D 792) and applying the results in the mixtures equation:

$$\rho_c = \rho_f v_f + \rho_m(1 - v_f - v_o) \quad (1)$$

where: v_f = fiber volume fraction
 v_o = void fraction (taken as 0)
 ρ_c = composite density
 ρ_f = fiber density
 ρ_m = cured resin density

This equation was solved for the fiber volume fraction (v_f).

Damping tests were carried out in a vacuum chamber, capable of 760 mm Hg., by recording the decay of free vibrations from cantilever beam specimens. The test specimens (details of the test setup are shown in figures 6 and 7) were fitted with tabs as described earlier and clamped in a very massive jig equipped with a remotely controlled releasing trigger that provided a step excitation input. Output from a strain gage transducer,

TABLE 1. CURE CYCLE PARAMETERS

<u>PARAMETER</u>	<u>PROCEDURE</u>
Heat up rate.	3 °C/min.
Intermediate dwell temp.	135 °C
Intermediate dwell time.	60± 5 min.
Vacuum application.	760mm. upon start.
Ext. pressure appl. (6 bar).	10 min. into dwell.
Vacuum dump.	2½ hr. after start.
External pressure dump.	4 hr. after start.
Cure temperature.	180 °C
Cure time.	120 min.
Cool down rate.	Natural cooling (4hr.).

Figure 4 - Temperature and pressure vs. time during cure cycle.

Figure 5 - Autoclave for preparing laminates serves double duty as a vacuum chamber for damping tests.

Figure 6 - Close up of cantilever beam with solenoid operated releasing trigger.

Figure 7 - Damping specimen dimensional details.

located at the specimen's base, was recorded on a digital storage oscilloscope and subsequently downloaded to an X-Y plotter for hardcopy and analysis. Specimens were tested over a range of initial deflections (300 - 1200 $\mu\epsilon$). The data in table II represents losses at approximately 600 $\mu\epsilon$.

Results and Discussions

The experimental data available at this writing are limited and preliminary since the majority of effort and time has been directed at refining the manufacturing and testing procedures. Experimental data is presented in table II. The normalized strength and moduli were obtained by the ratio of fiber volume fractions given by the formula:

$$M_{\text{nor}} = \frac{M_{\text{exp}}(.70)}{v_f}$$

where: M_{nor} = 70% normalized strength or modulus.
 M_{exp} = Actual strength or modulus from experiment.
 v_f = Actual fiber volume fraction.

The damping coefficient η in table II was obtained by the log decrement technique and is given by the formula:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{\pi n} \ln\left(\frac{X_0}{X_n}\right) = \tan \delta$$

where: X = Amplitude of vibration
 n = Number of cycles.
 δ = Phase angle between stress and strain.

It must be emphasized that air damping is extremely significant and can easily double the results [9, 10, 11]. Vibrational decay damping tests are sensitive to frequency and also a strong function of the vibrational amplitudes when instigated in air and hence testing was performed in vacuum to control these parasitic losses.

The prepregs of samples #6 and #7 were fabricated without using a heated bath. As mentioned earlier, the prepreg is difficult to handle and the samples tended not to have perfectly aligned fiber orientations. The damping results obtained may therefore not be comparable to those of the later specimens. The properties of samples #8 and #9 (strength and modulus) show that the specimen preparation was of a high calibre and it can be seen that the test results are similar to published literature values (see reference [12] at the bottom of table II) where CFRP made from commercial prepreg of the same fiber type was thoroughly examined.

Apart from using the log decrement technique, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed on a DuPont 1090/982 system approximating ASTM D 3418 for samples with the rubberized resin matrix. Damping coefficient results are shown in terms of $\tan \delta$ in figure 8. These graphs show the evident trend of higher damping as the fiber volume fraction decreases. This same trend is apparent when one studies the damping values in table II. Comparing plain resin samples #8 and #9 to similar fiber volume fraction specimens containing a rubber modified resin (EE1 and EE2), no significant change in damping coefficient due to the presence of the rubber modifiers is noticed. Damping values for the unmodified resin specimens agreed well with

TABLE 2. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND DAMPING

SPECIMEN No.	% CTBN CONTENT	PLY LAY-UP	BAGGING ARRANG.	FIBER VOL.%	STRENGTH MPa.	MODULUS GPa.	% ELONGATION AT FAILURE	NORMALIZED STRENGTH (GPa.)	NORMALIZED MODULUS (GPa.)	DAMPING ($\pm 5\%$)	FREQUENCY HZ.
6A	0.0	[0 ₈]	A	52.0	879	133	0.70	1183	179	0.0031	40.8
6B	0.0	[0 ₈]	A	52.0	1167	123	1.00	1571	165	0.0031	40.8
7A	0.0	[0 ₈]	A	54.0	1136	158	0.84	1473	200	0.0036	35.4
7B	0.0	[0 ₈]	A	54.0	1167	129	0.94	1571	164	0.0036	35.4
8	0.0	[0 ₈]	B	69.4	1590	176	0.91	1604	177	0.0021	44.7
9	0.0	[0 ₈]	B	70.7	1704	177	1.02	1678	175	0.0021	44.7
CC1	7.5	[0 ₈]	A	42.1	943	93	1.01	1568	155	0.0021	30.9
CC2	7.5	[0 ₈]	A	42.1	1066	112	0.96	1772	186	0.0021	30.9
DD1	7.5	[0 ₅]	A	36.3	904	102	0.86	1774	197	0.0025	39.1
DD2	7.5	[0 ₅]	A	36.3	748	94	0.86	1442	180	0.0025	39.1
EE1	7.5	[0 ₈]	B	65.3	1230	163	0.76	1319	175	0.0020	29.1
EE2	7.5	[0 ₈]	B	65.3	1172	140	0.84	1256	150	0.0020	29.1
AS GRAPHITE [13]	0.0	--	--	60.7	--	92	--	--	106	0.0017	109.0
NARMCO T300/5208 [9]	0.0	[0 ₈]	A	52.8	1104	124	0.99	1463	164	0.0042	67.8
NARMCO T300/5208 [12]	0.0	[0 ₈]	--	70.0	1503	181	0.80	1503	181	--	--

Figure 8 - Tan δ traces from DMA of Specimens CC1, DD2, EE1. (Note: Scale Tan δ of EE1 is 4/10 that of specimens CC1 and DD2).

values in the published literature [9, 13, 14]. Also the damping data taken from repeated tests on the same specimen gave consistent results. The above observations would indicate that at fiber volume fractions above 65% the contribution of the matrix to damping is minimal. Experimental results from Adams and Bacon [10] suggest that at 70% fiber volume fraction there may not exist any difference in laminate damping capacity between comparable unidirectional CFRP specimens differing only in the damping capacity of the matrix. In their tests the damping capacity of one matrix had 2.2 times the damping capacity of the other. Their mixture theory predictions however, indicated that one should expect a difference in damping.

Observations made by Scott and Philips [6] indicate that when using rubber additives in epoxies there is an enormous suppression of the modified resin's toughness when it is cured in a fiber reinforced laminate. Also the initial toughening effect is heavily dependent on the nature of the curing agent used, with increasing effectiveness for a given amount of rubber addition in the general order of: Aromatic amines, aliphatic amines, and anhydrides. The rubber and curing agent type is largely responsible for the phase structure in the cured resin, with compatible systems giving the finest particle size and uniform distributions and hence the greatest toughening effect.

Rubber additions much above 25% are held to cause a noticeable decline in mechanical properties [8, 15]. Furthermore, it is known that at these levels of rubber concentrations a lowering of glass transition temperature (T_g) is evident and it generally results in much poorer chemical / environmental resistance [15]. In our work with a 7.5% rubber addition, the evidence is yet too little to draw conclusions concerning the loss of mechanical properties, however it appears the losses, if any, are small. By the same token, for specimens of similar fiber volume fraction, the observed change in damping capacity between CFRP with plain and modified resin is also within the experimental error. (Compare samples #8 / #9 with EE1 / EE2 in table II).

Steps to be taken are the collection of enough data to draw statistically meaningful results. Further experiments will deal with a range of rubber concentrations and thereafter different grades of rubber additives. Fracture surfaces may also be examined using an electron microscope to determine rubber particle size distributions with a focus on the rubber particle / fiber interface where the shear damping effects sought are believed to originate.

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